

KEN AGRITECH PVT. LTD.

131 /1A, 216/1, Anchatageri Village, Karwar Road, Hubballi- 580 024, Karnataka, India. Tel: +91-836-2205699, 2970520, 2970521.

GSTIN: 29AAACK7136Q1ZW CIN:U01112KA1997PTC022721

Date: 11.11.2021

To,
Mr. Abul Firoz A
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Mangalore.

Dear Abdul Firoz,

Sub: Certificate of completion of Internship

This is to certify that Mr. Abdul Firoz A, student of College of Social Sciences and Humanities, 2nd Semester in MSW, has completed his Internship in our organization, under the guidance of Mr. Dhanaraj Naik, in the Department of Human Resources.

We hereby certify that his work was excellent.

We wish you all the Best! For your future endeavors.

Thanking you,

For Ken Agritech Pvt Ltd.,

Authorized Signatory

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

(PRIVATE UNIVERSITY ESTABLISHED UNDER KARNATAKA STATE ACT NO.42 OF 2013)

City Office: G.H.S.Road, MANGALURU - 575 001, Karnataka State, INDIA.

Phone No.: 0824-2425966, 2444891, Fax: 0824-2442766

E-mail: info@srinivasuniversity.edu.in website: www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Date: 01.12.2021

To,

Dr. Srinivas Bhat U.
Professor & HOD
Department of Psychiatry
K.S. Hegde Medical Academy
Mangalore.

Dear Sir,

Sub: Seeking Permission for Field Work Practicum

Greetings from Srinivas University, Mangaluru.

The College of Social Sciences and Humanities is offering Master of Social Work course since 2002. Since 2013, Srinivas Group of Colleges has been evolved to be a Private University (Karnataka Act No. 42.). We are happy to inform you that all these years we have been securing good results along with University Ranks. Srinivas University, for building competency among students has included skill based learning in its curriculum. We believe that Practical exposure through field work is the core element of study.

In this regard, our students are expected to undergo field work practicum for two days per week with reputed organizations to gain practical exposure. We understand that your esteemed organization would be an appropriate setting for our students for enthusiastic learning. Students are required to work on Wednesdays and Thursdays on all week days and required to follow the rules and regulations of your esteemed organization.

We herewith request you to kindly grant permission to Mrs. Poornima Ganiga (Reg. No.7SU20SW811), student of II Year MSW (Medical & Psychiatry specialisation) to undertake field practicum in your esteemed organization. Any misconduct or absenteeism from the students may please be brought to the notice of the University Supervisor immediately. Please contact Dr. Laveena D'Mello -9448611353. Kindly do the needful.

Thanking you,

Yours faithfully,

Dean

AKG MEMORIAL CO-OPERATIVE HOSPITAL

(A UNIT OF KANNUR CO-OPERATIVE HOSPITAL SOCIETY LTD.NO.C.834)

TALAP, KANNUR-670002

Email: akghospitalkannur@gmail.com

PH: 2762500

PRESIDENT: 2762451

SECRETARY: 2762401

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Ms. AGNAS J MARIYA**, First year MSW student at Srinivas University, Mangalore has successfully completed her 21 days (from 1st October 2021 to 21st October 2021) internship programme at AKG Memorial Co-operative Hospital, under the supervision of Consultant Clinical Psychologist Simna K T.

During this period of Internship Programme with us she was found hard working, interested and inquisitive.

Place: Kannur

Date:21-10-2021

For THE KANNUR CO-
HOSPITAL SOCIETY LTD.

SECRETARY

Softmind

center for cognitive behavioral science and applied behavior

SOFTMIND & LAKSHMI HOSPITAL

Bye pass junction, Aroor, Alappuzha, Kerala 688534

www.softmind.in | softmind.in@gmail.com

Phone: 04782672467 - 919646667409

19/11/2021

Ref.No:157231/11/21

To Whom It May Concern

This is to certify that Ms **Neethumol B** has undergone internship training at Softmind, Department of Psychology, Lakshmi Hospital, Aroor for a period of 1(one) month with proper satisfaction.

During this period, we found she is sincere, honest, and a dedicated intern with a professional attitude and very good knowledge about the job.

Her responsibilities were:

- 1) Plan psychological treatment programs that meet standard accreditation.
- 2) Review reports, case management review and visit psychiatric centres or hospitals to oversee procedure manual to assess need for further psychological services.
- 3) Develop, direct and participate in training programs.
- 4) Interview clients who presented with difficult and complex diagnostic problems and to assess their psychological status.
- 5) Review management of cases, assignments, case problems, issues and methods of treatment in collaboration with psychiatrist and other health care professionals to help develop comprehensive programs of therapy, evaluation and treatment.

Sincerely

PRASAD MK.Msc,(Psy)Mphil.(Psy) HPD
Licensed Clinical Rehabilitation Psychologist
RCI.:A50537

Softmind, Department of Psychotherapy, Lakshmi Hospital

PRASAD M.K, Msc (Psy) PGDRP, HPD (UK)
Licensed Rehab. Psychologist
Reg. No. RCI A50537

MindPlus
Psychological Services

CERTIFICATE PARTICIPATION / INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that Mr/ms Anju B Perumal has successfully completed one month on online clinical internship in psychology at mind plus psychological services, Thalassery, on (JANUARY 20-FEBRUARY 20, 2021).

I hereby certify her work Good to the best of my knowledge.

Date: 20/02/2021

Place: Thalassery

Managing Director

MindPlus Psychological Services

MindPlus

MindPlus
Psychological Services

CERTIFICATE PARTICIPATION / INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that Mr/ms Simi Simon has successfully completed one month on online clinical internship in psychology at mind plus psychological services, Thalassery, on (JANUARY 20-FEBRUARY 20, 2021).

I hereby certify her work **Good** to the best of my knowledge.

Date: 20/02/2021

Place: Thalassery

Managing Director

MindPlus Psychological Services

MindPlus

Mindplus

Psychological Services CERTIFICATE PARTICIPATION / INTERNSHIP

Binil T. V

This is to certify that Mr/Ms _____ has successfully completed one month on online clinical internship in psychology at mind plus psychological services, Thalassery (JANUARY 20-FEBRUARY 20, 2021).

I hereby certify that his work Good to the best of my knowledge.

Date: 20/02/2021

Managing Director

Place: Thalassery

Mindplus Psychological Services

THE
AVATAR
HOTEL

13th November, 2021

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Shreenidhi Nayak** from the College of Social Science & Humanities, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, has undergone an Internship for a period of 01 month in the **People Culture & Training Department** at **The Avatar Hotel Mangalore** from **01st October, 2021** till **31st October, 2021**.

During the tenure of the training period, we found her enthusiastic, hardworking and committed to the training goals.

We wish her the very best in all future endeavors.

Thank you,

Yours faithfully,
For The Avatar Hotel,

Mohammed Imran Khan
Complex General Manager

The AVATAR Hotel
& Convention

Nandigudde Road,
Attavar, Managalore 575 001

+91 82435 03900
+91 96069 20891
hello@theavatarhotel.com
www.theavatarhotel.com

BIGBAGS

INTERNATIONAL PVT. LTD.
DYNAMIC | DRIVEN | DEPENDABLE

Date: 30th October 2021

To Whomsoever It May concern

This is to certify that **Ms.Yakshitha Shetty (Reg.7SU20SW815)**, MSW Student of Srinivas University College of Social Science & Humanities has undergone Summer Internship in our Organization from 01stOctober 2021 to 30th October 2021.

During her internship training her performance was very good.

We wish her success in all future endeavors.

For **Big Bags International Pvt Ltd**

Authorised Signatory

CERTIFICATE

30-10-2021

This is to certify that **Ms. Jomisha Mathew.,** M.S.W 1st year, from Srinivas University, Mangalore, as successfully completed her Internship in the Department of Psychiatry as a part of M.S.W. course work from 06-10-2021 to 30-10-2021. During this period, she has been exposed to various therapeutic activities in De-Addiction, Psychiatry and Geriatric wards. She has also attended the departmental academic programmes which includes **Case Conferences, Seminars and Journal Clubs.**

Done to
30/10/21
Mrs. Agneita Aiman
Lecturer in PSW
Department of Psychiatry
KSHEMA

Shrinivasa Bhat U.
Dr. Shrinivasa Bhat U.
Prof & HOD
Department of Psychiatry
KSHEMA

Dr. Shrinivasa Bhat U.
Prof & HOD
Department of Psychiatry
KSHEMA, Bengalalatta
Mangalore - 575 013

DEPARTMENT OF MSW

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. JEEVAN** II year M.S.W student of Srinivas University, Mangalore was placed at our hospital for Internship training from 01.10.2021 to 30.10.2021 in Medical and Psychiatric setting. During this period he was mainly involved in:

- Studying the hospital- genesis, structure, functioning of various clinical inpatient and outpatient departments.
- Information regarding various services provided by the hospital to the patients through different schemes and programmes.
- Conducting case study of patients to ascertain their psychosocial background and respond to their Psycho-social needs in the hospital.
- Organization and conduct of case work, group work and group education programmes for patients and their caretakers.
- Counseling and providing psycho education to the patients and their family members.
- Attending the weekly conferences conducted by the agency supervisor.
- Participated in Blood Donation Camp conducted by YMCH in rural areas

His overall performance during the Internship training period was found good.

10.11.2021

HOD

Department of MSW

Dr. Mohammed Guthigar
HOD - MSW
Yenepoya (Deemed to be University)

Dr. A .V. Baliga Memorial Hospital

(A unit of Dr A. V. Baliga Charities, Mumbai)

6th Main, V.M.Nagar, Doddanagudde, UDUPI - 576 102.

Phone : (0820) 2535299, 2535399, 2535899, 2534899

E-mail:baligamemorialhospital@gmail.com Web.: www.avbmhospital.org

Ref:AVBMH/INT/NOV /2021

Date:06.11.2021

TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mrs Poornima Ganiga** . Student of Master of social work, Srinivas University, Mangalore has completed her Internship from **01.10.2021 to 31.10.2021 at our institution.**

During her tenure she has been exposed to various departments of psychiatry and allied departments in our institution and gained an exposure to certain of the competencies like case history taking, MSE, documentation of the work with applicable laws and regulations, professionalism at work.

She has actively participated in all the academic sessions. Her conduct was found to be good and her interpersonal relationship with superiors and other staffs and patients is appreciated. I wish her all best for her future.

Dr. P.V.Bhandary
Medical Director

Dr.A.V.Baliga Memorial Hospital,
Udupi

FATHER MULLER MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL

(Unit of Father Muller Charitable Institutions)
Fr Muller Road, Kankanady, Mangaluru - 575 002, INDIA

Phone : 0824-2238000
E-mail : mullerhospital@gmail.com
Website: www.fathermuller.edu.in

ESTD 1880

Fax : 0824 - 2436661

Ref. No: FMMC/ Psy/70/2021
Ref. No :

Date :
10.02.2021

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mrs. Caroline Lovely Dsouza, from Srinivas University, Mangaluru has completed the 'Field Work Placement' in Father Muller Medical College Hospital, Mangalore. She was posted during the academic year 2020-21, dated from 21.01.2021 to 10.02.2021.

She has fulfilled the required terms and conditions.

With regards,

Fr Rudolph Ravi D'Sa
ADMINISTRATOR

Date: 15th Feb 2021

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mis. Swathi Hegde a MSW student of Srinivas University, Mangalore, has undergone her Internship for a period from 20th January 2021 to 10th February 2021 in our company/organization.

During the above period, the performance and behavior of the Miss. Swati Hegde was satisfactory and best wishes for her career.

KANCOR INGREDIENTS LIMITED

Authorized Signature

